

TREASURE

Final Report & Implementation Guide

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Description version 1.0	This document summarizes Key Performance Indicators (KPI) measured at program uptake, main achievements, intended impact (short and long-term) and lessons learned through the TREASURE institutional pilot project, containing relevant information and links to documents relevant for others who may want to implement a similar program at their institutions, complemented by an implementation guide.

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¹Contributor roles follow the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT), <https://credit.niso.org/>.

List of Abbreviations

ARRA *Agreement for Reforming Research assessment*

ESRs *Early-stage researchers*

KPI *Key Performance Indicators*

RPO *research performing organization*

RRI *Responsible Research and Innovation*

RROR *Reproducible, reusable and open research*

UC *University of Coimbra*

TREASURE *Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research Training of Early-Stage Researchers*

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Glossary

Terminology	Definition or explanation
Early-stage researcher	<p>Same as First-stage researcher.</p> <p>«R1 - First Stage Researcher: Researchers doing research under supervision up to the point of a PhD or equivalent level of competence and experience.»</p> <p>(European Commission, 2011, Towards A European Framework For Research Careers²)</p>
Open Research	see <i>Open Science</i> .
Open Science	<p>«An inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.»</p> <p>(UNESCO Global Recommendation on Open Science, 2021, pp. 7)</p>
Recognize & reward	<p>«(...) reward as ‘a mostly <i>monetary</i> or <i>tangible</i> acknowledgment of someone’s efforts or success’ (Cotton et al., 2022). By contrast, recognition is largely <i>relational</i>, as captured in the acknowledgment of someone’s success through verbal or written feedback as well as via representational mechanisms, such as awards or prizes (Akafo et al., 2015).»</p> <p>UKRN, n.d., Source: https://recognition.ukrn-openresearch.ac.uk/glossary.html#recognition-and-reward</p> <p>Akafo, V., and Boateng, P. A. (2015), ‘Impact of reward and recognition on job satisfaction and motivation’. European Journal of Business and Management, 7(24), 112-124. https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/EJBM/article/view/25095.</p> <p>Cotton, C., Gifford, J. and Young, J. (2022), <i>Incentives and recognition: an evidence review. Practice summary and recommendations</i>. London: Chartered Institute of</p>

² Retrieved

from https://cdn5.euraxess.org/sites/default/files/policy_library/towards_a_european_framework_for_research_careers_final.pdf and <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52023DC0436> on February 13, 2025;

	<p>Personnel and Development, p. 3. https://www.cipd.org/uk/knowledge/evidence-reviews/evidence-financial-incentives/.</p>
<p>Replicability</p>	<p>In empirical sciences, replicable means to redo a previous study to confirm or infirm its results. Some variation is allowed.</p> <p>Following FORRT definition, « An umbrella term, used differently across fields, covering concepts of: direct and conceptual replication, computational reproducibility/replicability, generalizability analysis and robustness analyses. Some of the definitions used previously include: a different team arriving at the same results using the original author’s artifacts (Barba 2018); a study arriving at the same conclusion after collecting new data (Claerbout and Karrenbach, 1992); as well as studies for which any outcome would be considered diagnostic evidence about a claim from prior research (Nosek & Errington, 2020).»</p> <p>Barba, L. A. (2018). Terminologies for reproducible research. arXiv Preprint arXiv:1802.03311.</p> <p>Claerbout, J., & Karrenbach, M. (1992). Electronic documents give reproducible research a new meaning. SEG Technical Program Expanded Abstracts 1992. https://doi.org/10.1190/1.1822162</p> <p>Nosek, B. A., & Errington, T. M. (2020). What is replication? PLOS Biology, 18(3), e3000691. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000691</p>
<p>Reproducibility</p>	<p>It has many definitions, depending also on the specific research field and discipline. Following the FORRT definition (Parsons et al., 2022), « A minimum standard on a spectrum of activities (“reproducibility spectrum”) for assessing the value or accuracy of scientific claims based on the original methods, data, and code. For instance, where the original researcher’s data and computer codes are used to regenerate the results (Barba, 2018), often referred to as computational reproducibility. Reproducibility does not guarantee the quality, correctness, or validity of the published results (Peng, 2011). In some fields, this meaning is, instead, associated with the term “replicability” or ‘repeatability’.»</p> <p>See also Transparency.</p> <p>Barba, L. A. (2018). Terminologies for reproducible research. arXiv Preprint arXiv:1802.03311</p>

	<p>Peng, R. D. (2011). Reproducible Research in Computational Science. <i>Science</i>, 334(6060), 1226–1227. https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1213847</p> <p>Parsons, S., Azevedo, F., Elsherif, M. M., Guay, S., Shahim, O. N., Govaart, G. H., ... & Aczel, B. (2022). A Community-Sourced Glossary of Open Scholarship Terms. <i>Nature human behaviour</i>, 6(3), 312-318. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01269-4</p>
<p>Research Integrity</p>	<p><i>«It encompasses the basic responsibility of the research community to formulate the principles of research, to define the criteria for proper research behaviour, to maximise the quality, reliability, and robustness of research and its results, and to respond adequately to threats to, or violations of, good research practices. Research results in this context include, but are not limited to, publications, data, metadata, protocols, code, software, images, artefacts, and other research materials and methods.»</i></p> <p>Based on the following principles: «Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, methodology, analysis, and use of resources; Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting, and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full, and unbiased way; Respect for colleagues, research participants, research subjects, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage, and the environment; Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision, and mentoring, and for its wider societal impacts.»</p> <p>(ALLEA, 2023, European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity)</p>
<p>Responsible Research</p>	<p><i>«The process of aligning research and innovation to the values, needs and expectations of society»</i>, following the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) agenda and term introduced by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission, 2015a) to refer to the «process of aligning research and innovation to the values, needs and expectations of society» (European Commission, 2014³, pp. 1).</p>

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/rome-declaration-responsible-research-and-innovation-europe>

	<p>The European Commission considers 6 pillars: Gender equality, Science literacy and science education, Public engagement, Open access, Ethics, and Governance (European Commission, 2015a).</p>
Reusability	<p>To <i>«take steps to make research data and other research-relevant digital objects from public funding understandable and re-usable in the long term, including through the provision of high quality human-readable, machine-actionable, and open metadata and adequately maintained and supported bespoke algorithms, code, software, and workflows essential for re-use of data as free and open source.»</i></p> <p>(OECD, n.d.. Source: https://www.oecd.org/en/toolkits/access-to-research-data-from-public-funding-toolkit/technical-standards-and-practices/reusability.html)</p>
Transparency	<p><i>«...transparency is a prerequisite for reproducibility. Transparency represents the extent to which researchers provide sufficient information to enable others to reproduce the results.»</i></p> <p>(2019 National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2019). Reproducibility and Replicability in Science, pp. 63, available from https://www.nationalacademies.org/read/25303)</p>

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HOW TO READ THIS DOCUMENT

This document concerns the development and implementation of the TREASURE program (<https://www.uc.pt/en/iii/treasure/>) in the University of Coimbra (UC) that aims to *enable* the adoption of and *recognize & reward actual implementation* of a diverse set of **reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR)** practices and outputs in the research that is performed across disciplines, focusing its target population in researchers at earlier stages of their career - master and doctoral candidates. It was designed to be applicable to different disciplines, areas of knowledge, and ways to perform research.

In **Part 1 – Final Report** - you will find the **main achievements** from the institutional pilot project TREASURE with the development and implementation of a training & certification program at the University of Coimbra. Here, key performance indicators measured at the program uptake will be reported. In this part, we will highlight **lessons** taken from the **successes, hurdles and challenges** faced through this process. Finally, we will list **supporting resources** resulting from the project.

In **Part 2 – Implementation Guide** – we present **implementation steps** based on **lessons learned** that we hope useful for other organizations who may want to implement similar programs. Through this part, we will highlight **key points** from each section, the **CoARA commitments** addressed underlying each action, and the TREASURE **outputs** that can be used to support similar types of programs.

Final Report

1

1.1. Motivation and aims

Early-stage researchers⁴ (ESRs - those pursuing master's and PhD theses in research environments) are the future generation of qualified personnel doing research. Training this workforce for both academic and non-academic career paths and contexts while following best research standards and practices is therefore crucial.

The European Commission (EC) (2017a) has highlighted the opportunity brought by the *Open Science* (*Open Research*⁵ or *Open Scholarship*) paradigm to cultivate principles of transparency, collaboration, and research integrity, with transformative effects on how research is conducted. This shift can increase visibility, improve the efficiency of knowledge sharing, and strengthen research integrity, while fostering closer connections between researchers and society, and increasing scientific literacy of non-scientists (European Commission, 2017a). By simultaneously promoting rigor and transparency, open research is

⁴ According to the Commission Recommendation of 11 March 2005 on the European Charter for Researchers and on a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (2005/251/EC), «the term *Early-Stage Researcher* refers to researchers in the first four years (full-time equivalent) of their research activity, including the period of research training» (pp. L75/77). Although the European Charter & Code has been now revised (European Commission, 2025 – European Charter for Researchers. doi: 10.2777/5214248) with adoption of the previously defined term *First-stage researcher* to define the R1 career level - researchers up to the point of PhD (European Commission, 2011, Towards A European Framework For Research Careers), we maintained the terminology *Early-stage researchers* to designate researchers under training both as master's and PhD candidates.

⁵ Instead of *Open Science*, we will use the term *Open Research* in the remaining of the text to refer to science, research and scholarship in a more inclusive manner. However, the concepts of science, research and scholarship may be used interchangeably in the text.

expected to increase research reliability, credibility and quality (Allen & Mehler, 2019; Vazire, 2018). Open research covers a broad span of activities, practices and outputs, such as preregistration, registered reports, open methods, open and FAIR data, open source software and code, open hardware, open materials, open educational resources, open access, open infrastructures, citizen science and science communication, among other, and therefore requires wide and specific knowledge and skills, from technical to legal and ethical aspects (European Commission, 2017a; UNESCO, 2021).

It is therefore mandatory that researchers at all levels can have access to training and career professional opportunities to develop the appropriate skills and competencies they need to practice open research (European Commission, 2017a). There is currently a wide range of training available to enable responsible (e.g., Embassy of Good Science⁶), reproducible and open research practices (e.g., Auer et al, 2021). However, it is not enough to attend a training course on new research practices, as the training received is only effective if translated to the actual research performed (Heise et al., 2023). For real implementation, different strategies may be used, from building communities to adapting research assessment criteria and program requirements (Kohrs et al, 2023).

The European Commission recognized that for these practices to be adopted by the research community, incentives must be in place (European Commission, 2017b). This means that researchers and their research must be evaluated by a more comprehensive recognition and reward system in which open research practices and outputs, embedded in a wider set of criteria beyond metrics (i.e., both qualitative and quantitative indicators), are an integral part of the recruitment criteria, career progression, publishing, and funding assessment procedures (European Commission, 2017b). The delay in this cultural change has called for a concerted movement of initiatives and calls for action (e.g., DORA - San Francisco Declaration

⁶ A platform for research integrity and ethics resources and training, https://embassy.science/wiki/Main_Page;

on Research Assessment⁷; UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science⁸; Metrics Tide⁹; Hong Kong Principles¹⁰; CoARA¹¹ - Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment, and the resulting ARRA¹² - Agreement on Advancing Research Assessment, Arentoft et al, 2022; Benitez Monforte et al, 2026) in order to properly incentivize, recognize and reward researchers for more than publication of articles, funded projects, journal impact factor, and citation-related metrics (European Commission, 2017b).

The research assessment advancement has been mainly focused on the reform of established criteria and/or formats for funding applications, hiring and promotion procedures focusing on researchers who have completed their doctoral degree (e.g. introduction of narrative CVs, Aubert Bonn et al, 2025; Schmidt et al., 2021; Liang, Zhao & Li, 2024; see also: DORA Reformscape¹³, or CoARA Working Groups¹⁴ and CoARA Boost beneficiaries¹⁵).

Although middle career and senior researchers are in a good *position* to introduce change in the current research assessment system—they participate in recruitment and promotion procedures, more often review works for funding agencies and publishers (European Commission, 2017b), and serve as a role model to present and support responsible conduct of research in the students they supervise (Van Loon, et al., 2025; Haven et al., 2023)—ESRs seem to be at the forefront of introducing disruptive and innovative practices within their research groups (Kamal & Baten, 2025; Kent et al, 2022), being more prone to adopt new practices in line with open science and research integrity (Campbell et al, 2019; Haven et al,

⁷ Reference: DORA, <https://sfdora.org/>

⁸ Reference: <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about>

⁹ Reference: UKRI: The Metrics Tide: <https://www.ukri.org/publications/review-of-metrics-in-research-assessment-and-management/>

¹⁰ Reference: Resources on the Hong Kong principles: <https://www.wcrif.org/guidance/hong-kong-principles>

¹¹ Reference: Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment – CoARA, <https://www.coara.org/>

¹² Reference: CoARA: Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment: <https://www.coara.org/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>

¹³ Reformscape is a searchable collection of criteria and standards for hiring, review, promotion, and tenure from academic institutions created and curated by DORA, <https://sfdora.org/reformscape/>

¹⁴ <https://www.coara.org/wg-nc/working-groups/>

¹⁵ CoARA Boost community folder at the Zenodo repository hosting outputs from the beneficiaries of the CoARA Boost cascade funding program, https://zenodo.org/communities/coara_boost_cascade_funding/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

2023; Pizzolato & Dierickx, 2023a). Where supervisors lack the skills and knowledge in open research practices, ESRs may promote some type of “reverse mentoring” acting as agents of change in their own research environment (Algra et al., 2020; Abdi, 2022, p. 122; van Loon et al, 2025; Pizzolato and Dierickx, 2022). However, good research practices in line with open, responsible and reproducible research are associated with effort and time costs (Vazire, 2018; Allen & Mehler, 2019; Poldrack, 2019; Clavert et al., 2024). Lack of rewards for implementing new practices may impede change, promoting resistance in the supervisors, and demotivate ESRs who do not see their time and effort investment pay-off (Allen & Mehler, 2019).

The current project aimed to lay the groundwork to study if reforming ESRs assessments and providing incentives to implement responsible and open research practices and outputs act as a “Trojan horse” to improve practices within research groups and their host R&D units, amplifying reform efforts. We hope that rewarding ESRs for adopting responsible and open research practices and outputs in their thesis research, while engaging supervisors in this process, may accelerate culture change towards a performance in line with values of rigor, transparency, collaboration and research integrity.

The University of Coimbra (UC) is a research performing organization (RPO) covering a wide range of fields of knowledge – it has 11 units (faculties, institutes) of research and education, with only one of these units not providing formal education. UC graduate (master’s, PhD) programs rarely formally require or provide open research training or assess open research practices and outputs (exceptions exist – see Deliverable D.3 - Table 1, and Milestones M.3). Internationally, although some departments in Europe (Germany) have defined reward programs for both master’s and PhD graduate students, this approach is limited to a specific or few research fields (e.g. Leiden University Medical Center, University Medical Center Utrecht, psychology departments at LMU Munich and the University of Münster) (Algra et al., 2020; Hatch & Curry, 2020; Khors et al., 2023). Under our current knowledge, this pilot was the first formal *institutional* cross-faculties attempt to address these issues.

This pilot project aimed to meet the needs of different research and scholar fields across the UC, developing a program in which *training* is necessary, but the critical dimension is the recognition & reward of graduate students for actual *implementation* of RROR practices and outputs in their research theses. During the past one-year grant, we have created a Local Advisory Board made of those directly involved in the assessment exercise – course coordinators, supervisors, master’s and PhD students from different disciplinary and research fields; we were supported by an additional panel of experts – the External Advisory Board members – who provided us with advice and offered their expertise to develop solutions. With them, we have co-created a list of practices and outputs that are relevant for their fields of knowledge, assessment criteria targeting quality and a training & certification program to support and reward students who implement these practices/outputs in their theses. ESRs who implement specified practices and outputs within their thesis research can obtain this badge alongside their degree.

In the long-term, and as enabling factor, we will work to transform the certification into a formal accreditation that recognizes the knowledge and skills earned by the TREASURE program participants, and to embed the accredited skills into hiring & promotion criteria for UC entry-level research positions. In this path, we expect that not only participating students benefit from the change, but also their colleagues, supervisors, courses & course coordinators, and researchers within their research units, changing the research environment in a slow-paced but solid movement.

1.2. Why reproducible, reusable and open research

Although alternative terms could have been used to describe the identity of the TREASURE program, we chose terminology that promotes clarity while allowing for a broad and flexible range of practices and outputs beyond *open access* publications. Specifically, we translated the concept of *responsible* [research] (European Commission, 2015a; European Commission,

2014¹⁶) into the threefold concept of ‘*reproducible*’, ‘*reusable*’ and ‘*open research*’. These concepts encompass other pillars of the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) EC agenda, either explicitly—through practices such as citizen science and public engagement, and science communication and policy briefs—or implicitly, as the program’s practices and outputs assume compliance with legal and ethical standards, respect inclusivity, diversity, and equity, and aim to improve science literacy and education for both researchers and non-researchers.

Reproducibility and *replicability* may not be equally feasible across all fields of research and scholarship, nor embrace the same core relevance in every discipline (Ulpts & Schneider, 2025a, 2025b). Although allowing variation in its definition (LeBel et al, 2018 - Appendix A¹⁷; Ulpts & Schneider, 2025a) and operationalization (LeBel et al, 2018), reproducibility and replicability are central in psychology, neuroscience, and other experimental fields (Botvinik-Nezer & Wager, 2022). In contrast, there is ongoing debate as to whether these concepts apply to the humanities as a whole (Patton, 2025), or only to their empirical components (Peels, 2019) due to the diverse epistemological systems and ways of knowing (Ulpts & Schneider, 2025b). Projects such as TIER2 (<https://tier2-project.eu/>) have contributed to clarifying the concepts of reproducibility and replicability by proposing a reconciling terminology based on *practices* (redoing, enabling) and *epistemic functions* (purpose), emphasizing that both *relevance* and *feasibility* of redoing and enabling must always be considered (Ulpts & Schneider, 2025a, 2025b). Given the multi- and interdisciplinary nature of the TREASURE pilot and resulting program, it is important that these concepts respect epistemic diversity and situate these in specific knowledge production modes (Ulpts & Schneider, 2025a, 2025b).

Open research brings benefits for different stakeholders, from researchers, to institutions, funders and the public. Overall, it allows transparency about methods and results, enabling

¹⁶ European Commission: Rome Declaration on Responsible Research and Innovation in Europe (21 November 2014), retrieved February 12, 2026, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/rome-declaration-responsible-research-and-innovation-europe> .

¹⁷ Supplementary materials for the article: Appendix A: Clarification of Reproducibility-Related Terms, <https://osf.io/gpu3a/>

verification by others, promoting research integrity and quality; by generating a more diverse set of outputs and their reuse research waste is reduced, while also allowing a more broad assessment of researchers' activities beyond publications (UK Reproducibility Network, 2024). Open research can be adopted across disciplines while respecting constraints related to data protection (Bobrov et al., 2024; Plale, 2019), intellectual property (Music, 2025; Nuechterlein et al., 2023; ALLEA, 2022), and research security (OECD, 2025). Openness alone is necessary but is not sufficient to ensure reproducibility and reusability of practices and outputs (e.g., Hardwicke et al., 2018). Digital outputs must be shared with appropriate quality standards (Bechhofer et al, 2016) and in accordance with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles to ensure reuse (Wilkinson et al, 2016). In fact, reusability of both practices (including methods) and outputs should be promoted to minimize research waste (Houts et al., 2022; Ramsey et al., 2022).

Together, reproducibility, replicability, reusability, and openness enable others to generate new insights from prior research and scholarship and are increasingly recognized by organizations as markers of research quality (Arentoft et al., 2022; Morris & Saenen, 2024). But more systematic studies are needed to evaluate the diverse forms of impact of open research adoption (Catalano et al., 2025; Cole et al., 2024).

TREASURE holds the mission of recognize and reward ESRs - graduate students - for implementing *reproducible, reusable, and open research* (RROR) practices and outputs in their research theses, aiming to improve research practices and their outputs. For this, it focused on the *enabling* foundation pillars of providing both (a) training and support, and (b) recognition and reward. Through this project, we defined a groundwork for future studies to test whether and how reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs improve research quality and its impact.

1.3. Pilot timeline

We divided the TREASURE pilot project into two major phases: in the first half we would co-create the list of RROR practices and outputs and the program to provide training and certify the implementation of the practices/outputs; and in the second half we would implement the program, open it for enrolment, and deliver the training and support to the students (**Figure 1**). In between, we would develop materials and resources to define the program and support the students in the implementation of the practices and outputs.

Figure 1. Timeline for the institutional pilot project TREASURE (adapted from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15786585>).

1.4. Outcomes & Lessons learned

In this section we highlight how we developed the pilot - creating the advisory boards and running the board sessions; and the main outputs from this co-creative process, adding lessons learned which were particularly relevant for the Implementation Guide in the second part of this document.

1.4.1. Setting the ground to develop the program

- **Creating the Advisory boards**

To build the program, we considered both local and external members to take part in the co-creation process. For the **Local Advisory Board (LAB)**, the key actors directly targeted and necessary for the program to work were involved. These were master's and PhD candidates, course coordinators and researchers that were PIs and/or supervisors - from different research fields, faculties and research & development units, as well as connected to different courses – we invited members adding their perspective. They were considered the core members when it came to discuss and define:

1. the practices and outputs supported and rewarded through the program (adaptable to different research fields)
2. the assessment criteria & procedures to award the certificate
3. the agreement to use to ensure that students and supervisors agree on the implementation plan
4. the qualitative peer review procedures to ensure that criteria were met
5. options for types of reward to offer students (and supervisors and course coordinators) beyond an certificate

CoARA Commitments:

Commitment 6: *Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes - 6.2 Criteria for projects and researchers: With the direct involvement of researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria, tools and processes for the assessment of research projects, research teams and researchers that are adapted to their context of application*

Commitment 7: *Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use*

Commitment 8: *Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition*

Table 1. Successes and challenges found during the creation of the Local Advisory Board.

Local Advisory Board (LAB)	
Members Total N: 27	
What worked / Positive aspects / Successes	Hurdles / Negative aspects / What didn't work
Representation of 9 in 11 faculties/organic units of the University of Coimbra, with at least 1 course represented from each (total: 18), through coordinators and/or students (master/PhD)	Difficulty in defining the strategy to select/invite members for the local board.
The number of members across the 5 sessions varied, with some core members attending most of the meetings. Despite absence of many members across the sessions, the high number of members (total N=27) allowed representation of different fields across time	Choices to balance board size while ensuring a wide representation of disciplines/faculties and roles (investigators, early stage researchers, course coordinators)
LAB members represent 12 different research & development units of the University, extending the initial plan of having 5 units. The results give a wide interdisciplinary dimension to the program	LAB was constituted by 27 members, a number that could place into question its feasibility – it was impossible to ensure the presence of all members in all meetings
Opportunity to engage with ESRs (Master's and PhD candidates), supervisors, middle-career and more senior researchers, and course coordinators from different research fields	Drop-out of members in later sessions
Members proposed practices and outputs that were not initially considered	
LAB members acted as later ambassadors to disseminate the program	

Legend: LAB, Local advisory board; EAB, External advisory board; ESRs, Early-stage researchers.

External members were invited to an **External Advisory Board (EAB)** to provide additional expertise and insights from other institutions:

1. Supporting the project core team and the Local board in the development of strategies for implementing the new program and associated training

2. Providing advice on external training resources to fill gaps identified at the UC
3. Supporting problem solving by sharing solutions that have worked in their institutions, whenever obstacles are identified.

Table 2. Successes and challenges found during the creation of the External Advisory Board.

External Advisory Board (EAB) Members	
Members Total N: 5	
What worked / Positive aspects / Successes	Hurdles / Negative aspects / What didn't work
Diversity of contexts: academia, funding agencies, international and national contexts	Challenging to schedule meetings with everyone to facilitate collaborative discussion

Legend: EAB, External advisory board.

- **Sessions for co-creation of the TREASURE program**

During the development of the program, we held 5 meetings with the Local board, and 3 meetings with the External board.

To plan the meetings, we used available resources such as the SCOPE framework – a structured five-stage model for evaluating responsibly by which assessment approaches can be designed and implemented, as well as probed, developed by the International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) Research Evaluation Group (Himanen et al., 2024). It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as check existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation.

The **LAB five meetings** held the following structure:

1. Present the TREASURE project and start creating the **list** of rewarded practices and outputs (assessing the importance of concepts of reproducibility, reusability and openness across fields; identification of reproducible, reusable, open practices and outputs across and within research disciplines)
2. **Field specificities** to consider in the list of practices and outputs; added **value** of the program, **barriers** and solutions during the implementation of these practices/outputs
3. **Criteria** to assess the practices/outputs within the theses (high-level & field-specific criteria)
4. **Procedures** to provide formal recognition (feasibility) and rewards offered
5. **Evaluation** criteria **frameworks** to assess the implementation (feedback & probing)

During the **three EAB meetings**, we approached the following topics:

- Completeness, feasibility and generalizability of the **list** of practices and outputs
- **Restrictions** on openness that could be used to justify limits or avoid the implementation of the practices and outputs (e.g. data protection, intellectual property rights, research security)

CoARA Commitments:

Commitment 1: *Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research*

Commitment 2: *Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators*

Commitment 6: *Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes - **6.2 Criteria for projects and researchers:** With the direct involvement of researchers at all career stages, review and develop criteria, tools and processes for the assessment of research projects, research teams and researchers that are adapted to their context of application*

Commitment 7: *Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use*

Commitment 8: *Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition*

- Feasibility, potential problems and added value of the **procedures** defined for the program
- **Evaluation** criteria **frameworks** to assess the implementation (feedback & probing)
- **Agreement** to be set between the student and the supervisor (feedback & probing)
- Identified **challenges**

Table 3. Successes and challenges found during the meetings with the Local Advisory Board.

Local Advisory Board Meetings	
Meetings total: 5	
Successes / Positive aspects / What worked	Hurdles / Negative aspects / What didn't work
Raised important questions related with recognition / reward: supervisors (and others who are involved) also need to be rewarded; and that “rewards need to be real incentives, and not just stickers”	Introducing new practices to the community took time, as practices were unfamiliar to many and awareness differed across fields
Suggested relevant recognition & reward mechanisms or options, in addition to the certification, that were relevant for each group (students, course coordinators, supervisors)	Expressed fears and concerns related to sharing (in particular, sharing research data)
Discussing added value of the program and barriers	Finding relevant rewards and drivers that can motivate change
	Managing epistemic diversity (relevance, feasibility, translation)
	Find overlapping schedules to hold the meetings, ensuring enough <i>quorum</i>

Tables 3 and **4** summarize key points on what worked and what were the challenges during the 8 meetings held with the LAB (Table 3) and the EAB (Table 4).

Table 4. Successes and challenges found during the meetings with the External Advisory Board.

External Advisory Board Meetings	
Meetings total: 3	
What worked / Positive aspects / Successes	Hurdles / Negative aspects / What didn't work
Added practices to the list	Some suggestions on how to reward students implementing RROR were offered by institutions that are already considering responsible research practices in their hiring and promotion criteria. However, these were not (yet) feasible to implement at the UC as they required already some changes in the research culture (e.g., adoption of some of the practices and outputs in promotion criteria)
Sharing of relevant use cases and institutional materials	Find times to hold the meetings that worked for everyone

Legend: RROR, reproducible, reusable and open research; UC, University of Coimbra.

1.4.2. Main outputs from the co-creation process

- **List of reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs, and evaluation criteria**

As a result of the co-creation process, we created a list of practices and outputs, with potential adaptation for different fields of knowledge. Initially, this contained additional practices or outputs (Milestone M.2) that were later excluded from the program (Deliverable D.2) as we did not have experts and/or training resources (Milestone M.3) at the UC to provide training and support implementation.

TREASURE output:

Deliverable D.2: report containing the list of practices and outputs - potentially applicable and adaptable to different disciplines and study types -, associated assessment criteria, and procedures considered for the TREASURE program.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.157865>
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Although we initially categorized all rewarded things as practices, we later divided the list into practices and outputs. *Practices* are a methodology or collection of methodologies used to produce, to report or to disseminate research outputs, whereas *Outputs* are the product of one or more research practices that can be shared on a repository and are attributed a unique and persistent identifier (e.g. DOI, handle). For an overview, see **Figure 2**.

CoARA Commitments:

Commitment 1: Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

Figure 2. List of the reproducible, reusable, and open research practices and outputs currently included in the TREASURE program (adapted from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15786585>).

For a summary of key points on what worked and the challenges found during the development of the list of practices and outputs with the LAB and the EAB, see **Table 5**.

Table 5. Successes and challenges found during the development of the list of practices and outputs and associated evaluation criteria.

Successes / Positive aspects / What worked	Hurdles / Negative aspects / What didn't work
LIST: creation of a 16 RROR practices and outputs list adaptable to different research fields	LIST + CRITERIA: Managing epistemic diversity (importance/relevance, applicability/feasibility, translation)
LIST: addition of practices relevant for the members (reporting null results)	LIST: Differences in importance/relevance & applicability/feasibility of reusability, reproducibility and open research across research fields
LIST: consideration of specific language, acquiring	LIST: Translating what the practices and outputs look like – names of practices/outputs and implementation differ among fields & projects
LIST: adding specific examples from different fields (e.g. practices nomenclature, repositories, journals)	CRITERIA: Define assessment criteria for outputs that can take many different formats (e.g., science communication, citizen science)
LIST + CRITERIA: opportunity to discuss with middle career and more senior researchers, librarians, science managers, open science officers connected to different open science and research assessment initiatives – by connecting with projects with members inside and external to the UC	

Legend: LAB, Local advisory board; RROR, Reproducible, reusable and open research; UC, University of Coimbra.

- **TREASURE training, implementation & certification program**

As the main output of the TREASURE pilot, we created a training, implementation & certification program (<https://www.uc.pt/en/iii/treasure/outputs/curricular-units-2025-2026/>) which will allow us to raise awareness, deliver training, involve both the students and their supervisors, support the implementation of RROR practices and outputs, and reward the students who participate in the program. We opened the TREASURE program in September 2025 and this is now offered to all Master's and PhD candidates of the University of Coimbra. The program takes the form of two optional, extra-ECTS and semestral course units that they can add to their curricula.

- **Reproducible reusable and open research I - Introduction to Certification:** to select the practices or outputs to implement and agree on an implementation plan with their supervisor
- **Reproducible reusable and open research II - Implementing the Certification):** to check the implementation and attribute the certification

TREASURE output:

Opt-in program with two course units developed:

<https://www.uc.pt/en/iii/treasure/outputs/curricular-units-2025-2026/>

Students are motivated to (a) choose few practices/outputs and the ones that best fit their research field, workplan and specific study, and (b) to implement them well.

Students will receive the certification if they:

- a) Select RROR practices and/or outputs from the list covered in the program and define an implementation plan (course unit I)
- b) successfully finish the program, i.e. implement with quality and in their research thesis the RROR practices and/or outputs selected (course unit II). The number of practices/outputs to implement depend on the cycle of studies and workload required - 1 or 2 (Master's) or 2 or 3 (PhDs).

CoARA Commitments:

Commitment 1: Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

Successes and challenges faced during development, implementation and opening of the program procedures are presented in **Table 6**.

The program will continue to run in the next academic years. We believe this training & certification program, by formally recognizing students who successfully implement a wide set of RROR practices and outputs in their thesis, will act as a leverage for change and will leave a lasting impact.

Table 6. Successes and challenges faced during development, implementation and opening of the program procedures.

Successes / Positive aspects / What worked	Hurdles / Negative aspects / What didn't work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving the institution leadership (Vice-rectory for Education) in the definition of the program procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrating the program into regulations and procedures (what works locally) • Practical constraints in structuring the program: options, challenges, what works locally
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Program procedures allow formal recognition of the training and acquired skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives still fall behind: mechanisms to reward the students involved are insufficient to enhance competitiveness of CVs for research positions without broader changes in research assessment criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course coordinators (included in the LAB) were true ambassadors of the program, either by alerting directors from their faculties, or by encouraging their students to enroll in the program 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to reward the supervisors that actively contribute and motivate their students to participate
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opening of the program in the academic year 2025/26 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can we motivate students to participate? (effort vs efficiency, barriers)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrolment of students from courses not initially represented in the LAB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timelines (match across master's and PhD programs in general, as well as specific courses requirements and time points – e.g. PhD project proposal defense in year 1)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Registration of 18 students in course unit I, and of 9 in course unit II during the program first edition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheduling: finding overlapping schedules for students from different courses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course unit I (1st semester 2025/26) - Submission of Implementation Plans: 8 students successfully submitted their plans (see Table 8), selecting 11 practices/outputs from the 15 options available (*) 	

Legend: LAB, Local advisory board; CV, curriculum vitae; (*) Author Contribution Statements are a mandatory practice.

To monitor and measure impact at program uptake (first edition) and through the years, we defined **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)**. We have reviewed the KPIs from the original workplan and here detail these reviewed KPIS, detailing them in the text and reporting them in **Table 7, Table 8** and **Table 9**. As new KPIs, we define KPI #2 for variables related to students

who have enrolled in the TREASURE program in the academic year 2025/26, and KPI#4 for variables related to the practices and program held sessions.

- KPI1
 - the number of ESRs who participate in UC trainings after disseminating Deliverable 3

For the earlier defined KPI1 this number could not be tracked and reported given the format in which we defined the program – course units within academic years, requiring enrolment in the program (this means all participating students are registered in the program).

- KPI2:
 - number of students enrolled in both course units
 - number of faculties and courses with participating students

For this academic year (program first edition), we had 18 students enrolled in the first course unit from 10 (6 PhD programs, 4 Master's programs) different programs – these students come also from courses not represented in the Local Advisory Board. It was expected to have fewer students in the 2nd course unit as only the master's students can finish their thesis in the same academic year, whereas the PhD students should only finish their theses in the next academic years (**Table 7, KPI #2**).

Table 7. Key performance indicators to monitor the TREASURE training & certification program: KPI#2 – participating students and originating faculties.

Program First edition 2025/26	
KPI #2 Number of students who have enrolled in the program by selecting the course unit	KPI #2 Number of education & research units* and of courses with participating students (units/courses)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course unit I (planning): 18 • Course unit II (implementation): 9 (PhD students are expected to enroll in subsequent years) 	<p>Course unit I (planning):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E&R units: • Courses: 10 (6 PhD courses, 4 master courses) <p>Course unit II (implementation):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E&R units: 3 • Courses: 6 (3 PhD courses, 3 master courses)

Legend: Education & research units refer to faculties or to organic units (interdisciplinary or in specific disciplines) – these differ from research & development units, which are mostly connected to research performance and hosting of students, but that do not provide education (1st cycle, 2nd cycle or 3rd cycle) on their own.

- KPI3:
 - pre-selected practices/outputs (relevant for their studies and that raised most interest)
 - number of students participating in the sessions on specific practices/outputs

Table 8 (KPI #3) presents the practices/outputs that raised most interest among the students (i.e., $n \geq 6$ students have pre-selected this practice/output) from the list of 16 practices/outputs covered in the program (see **Figure 1**). However, all 15 practices/outputs had at least 1 student interested (i.e., it was pre-selected by at least 1 student for implementation in their research thesis).

- KPI4:
 - the number of ESRs who sign planning agreements
 - the practices that they plan to implement
 - number of research groups with participating students

Exact information on what practices/outputs students selected to implement in their implementation plans (required for the first course unit, 1st semester 2025/26) is outlined in **Table 9 (KPI #4)**. For the second course unit (to check implementation and provide certification), we had 9 registered students (mostly Master’s students who can finish the two course units in 1 academic year; or PhD students who are finishing their studies and can still implement some of the practices/outputs). The practice of Author contribution statements is mandatory. At the end of the first unit, 8 (out of 18) students successfully submitted their Implementation Plans (**Table 9**). Of note, severe damage due to a hurricane and extensive flooding for several weeks in Portugal (late January/late February 2026) after the course deadline prevented some students from submitting.

Table 8. Key performance indicators to monitor the TREASURE training & certification program II: KPI#3 - pre-selection of practices and outputs and attended training sessions.

Program First edition - Course unit I (planning): total N = 18	
KPI #3 Pre-selected practices (number of students who showed interest in the practice/output)	KPI #3 Number of students attending the practices/outputs sessions*
1) Reporting guidelines (n = 10 students) 2) Open step-by-step methods (n = 9) 3) Evidence synthesis techniques (n = 8) 4) Data sharing (n = 7) 5) Preprints (n = 6) 6) Reporting null results (n = 6) 7) Open Educational Resources (n = 6) 8) Science communication (n = 6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the program: 11 • Step-by-step protocols: 8 • Data sharing: 4 • Preregistration + Registered reports: 3 • Reporting null results + Preprints: 7 • Open educational resources: 3 • Open-source code: 1 • Science communication: 5 • Citizen science: 3

Legend: KPI, Key performance indicator. () Some practices considered in the TREASURE program list were held online during the Love Methods Week 2026, co-organized by one of the TREASURE team. For these sessions (Unique resource identifiers; Replication studies; Evidence synthesis techniques; Reporting guidelines), attendance was not tracked.*

Table 9. Key performance indicators to monitor the TREASURE training & certification program III: KPI#4 – first course unit output: selected practices, outputs and implementation plans submitted.

Program First edition - Course unit I (planning): total N = 18		
KPI #4 Selected practices/outputs outlined in the submitted Implementation Plan	KPI #4 Number of students submitting the Implementation Plans	KPI #4 Number of R&D centers / research groups with students submitting Plans
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step-by-step methods (n = 3) • Data sharing (n = 3) • Preregistration (n = 2) • Reporting guidelines: (n = 2) • Science communication (n = 2) • Unique resource identifiers (n = 2) • Evidence synthesis techniques (n = 1) • Open source code (n = 1) • Reporting of null results (n = 1) • Preprints (n = 1) • Open educational resources (n = 1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N = 8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&D centers: 6 • Research groups: 7

Legend: KPI, Key performance indicator; N or n, Number of students.

We ran a post course unit survey to understand what worked best and what could be improved (**Table 10**). We will do this through each program edition for continuous improvement of the program, in line with quality management principles (work in progress).

Table 10. Feedback received for the participating students (first course unit) after opening of the program procedures.

Successes / Positive aspects / What worked	Hurdles / Negative aspects / What didn't work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching staff: lecture and support provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of some practices/outputs in specific fields (e.g., Law) may be challenging
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching dynamics: hands-on exercises within session 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheduling challenges: lack of fixed schedule; most sessions were held in-person
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course is implementation-oriented (implement practice/output in thesis/specific research project) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course structure and phasing: overwhelmed by information - turn the experience smoother
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New relevant info: new knowledge and tips that can improve research thinking & practice 	

1.4.3. Assessment of institutional RROR maturity level

- **Mapping and gap analysis of training resources and capacity to support the implementation of the practices – institutional and external**

The mapping of available training resources and capacity (through human resources) at the University of Coimbra was performed through a gap analysis exercise (Milestone M.3). The aim of the exercise was to identify resources that could support and facilitate the training, adoption

and implementation of a diverse set of practices and outputs with quality. This proved to be useful to identify the current maturity level (i.e. capacity built) of the institution in terms of reproducible, reusable and open research practices. Moreover, it allowed to identify processes that may be improved to meet & reach strategic institutional goals. A summary of positive and negative points is presented in

Table 11.

CoARA Commitments:

***Commitment 1:** Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research*

***Commitment 5:** Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organizational changes committed to*

Table 11. Successes and challenges identified during the mapping and gap analysis of training resources and capacity at the University of Coimbra to support the TREASURE program.

Successes / Positive aspects / What worked	Hurdles / Negative aspects / What didn't work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synergies built with institutional leadership, namely the UC Vice-rector for Culture, Communication and Open science and his team, which were monitoring open science indicators, facilitating identification of existing training resources related to open science practices and outputs (Milestone 3 and Deliverable 3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of indicators for open science at the university level did not completely overlap practices/outputs covered by the TREASURE project, requiring adjustments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 3 resources useful both for University of Coimbra students and external students, other researchers or stakeholders - the list contains training resources options for different publics interested in implementing RROR practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping of institutional training resources was not a straightforward task as there is no centralized registry that records all training events and initiatives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although some trainings are dated events and may therefore become unavailable for future use, many others refer to deliverable of projects, toolkits, online lectures that will remain available 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task allowed us to verify current maturity of the institution to provide training in particular RROR practices and outputs, contributing to identify gaps (two initially included practices were removed from the RROR list to support) 	

Legend: RROR, Reproducible, reusable and open research; TREASURE, Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research training of Early Stage Researchers; UC, University of Coimbra.

1.4.4. List of TREASURE supporting outputs (detailed in the boxes above)

To support the program and provide valuable resources for those involved, the pilot project delivered the outputs listed in **Table 12**.

Table 12. List of outputs from the TREASURE pilot project to support the implementation of the program at the University of Coimbra.

Name	Content and Goal
Deliverable D.2 – Report: Reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) practices and outputs list, criteria and procedures. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15785596	This document includes the list of reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs that will be taught and supported in the TREASURE training, implementation and certification program , at the University of Coimbra. For each practice and output, assessment criteria were defined to promote and ensure quality in the implementation. The program design, structure and related activities are outlined in the procedures section, presenting an institutional solution on how to develop and embed this type of program in an RPO.
Deliverable D.3 – Training program: List of training resources to support implementation of reproducible, reusable and open research. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093855	This document includes the list of training programs and resources identified to support the implementation of the previously outlined practices and outputs in the TREASURE project deliverable D.2, following assessment and gap analysis of training available at the University of Coimbra (UC) (Milestone M.3). The resources listed concern education and training programs existing either at UC or available resources from external sites , whenever gaps were identified within the UC. The list serves both the students enrolling in the UC program, as all other students, mentors, supervisors, researchers who may want to implement these practices/outputs

Legend: RPO, Research performing organization; RROR, Reproducible, reusable and open research; TREASURE, Transforming Research Assessment through Responsible Research training of Early Stage Researchers; UC, University of Coimbra.

1.5. Envisioned impact pathway

After the pilot, and through each academic year and TREASURE program edition, we will continue to monitor and improve the program to maximize impact and extend this strategy to other UC research & education units, courses, R&D centers and research teams. Institutional recognition of successful implementation of RROR practices and outputs in master’s and PhD thesis through the TREASURE program will reward efforts and participation in the program.

The TREASURE project team, which includes members of the Meta-research and Research Improvement research team, funded by the EXCELSIOR ERA Chair project, will contribute to follow-up evaluations, discussions on program impact and broader adoption of RROR practices and outputs within R&D programs, groups, and works. TREASURE will raise awareness about the relevance of research assessment reform within UC and accelerate movement towards the Agreement for Reforming Research assessment (ARRA). The community building and lessons learned will allow us to implement research assessment reforms more efficiently and effectively.

In the following sections we present the short-term and long-term expected impact.

1.5.1. Short-term (through participating students)

Within 1 year from the project start date, Master's candidates in the first TREASURE cohort will have completed the program, and PhD candidates will be working on implementing the practices and outputs that they selected in their project. The second cohort of students will enrol, allowing us to extend and refine the program, while strengthening our connections with graduate programs across the university. We will begin to accumulate examples of strong implementation of different practices/outputs from various research fields, hold an event to showcase the work of students who implemented practices/outputs well to inspire others, and assess the number and quality of practices and outputs implemented among students who enrolled in TREASURE and matched control students who did not participate.

Within 5 years from program start, we will have a better understanding of which practices apply to different fields, and many examples of what excellent implementation looks like in different research areas. Increased uptake of rewarded practices and outputs across the university will create a path to discuss integration of these practices and outputs into research assessment criteria for other researchers within the university, so that supervisors who support their students in implementing reproducible, reusable and open practices

and outputs are also rewarded. We will be able to assess the uptake of relevant practices and outputs across the university.

In the short term (1 to 5 years), we aim to:

- **encourage supervisors and other researchers to adopt new practices and outputs:** the program directly involves the supervisor by asking the students to discuss with him/her diverse reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) practices/outputs included in the list co-created in the TREASURE program, which practices/outputs best fit the work plan and can be implemented, and to agree on an implementation plan. This plan needs to be approved by the supervisor. Through this student-supervisor dyad and promoted discussion, we hope to motivate the supervisors to adopt a wider set of practices/outputs, in line with RROR, promoting skills in the students, and inspiring other researchers in the host institution, R&D centre, lab or research group in which the student is developing his/her research;
- **collect examples of good research practices and outputs from different fields to inspire others:** from each edition of the program, we aim to collect examples of good RROR practices and outputs from different fields that can be used to inspire others – students, colleagues from their research groups, supervisors and more senior researchers from their academic and research environments.

1.5.2. Long-term (Planned)

In the long term (beyond 5 years), we aim to:

- reward supervisors whose students consistently participate, and all that have actively promoted RROR adoption and implementation, namely course coordinators, course programs and faculties – the program was built in co-creation with students, supervisors and course coordinators, and course coordinators have been true ambassadors of this program in their faculties;

- develop procedures to recognize programs and faculties that consistently implement practices and outputs – to foster long term change, recognizing & rewarding course programs and faculties that have moved forward in recognizing and valuing a diverse set of RROR practices/outputs is key to promote change and keep all involved motivated. We will work to find solutions that work in the University of Coimbra for RROR adoption, similarly to what has been previously done with more sustainable behaviours at UC and for which the UC is now recognized;
- changing hiring & promotion criteria to consider high-quality and impactful RROR practices and outputs - by building awareness and recognition of the relevance of reproducible, reusable and open research skills, we aim to facilitate their incorporation into hiring & promotion criteria.

1.6. Conclusions

During the design, development and implementation of the TREASURE program, we have connected with many different stakeholders in the University of Coimbra and beyond.

By involving those directly involved – representatives of Masters’ and PhD candidates, supervisors and course coordinators (local advisory board, LAB) – in the definition of a list of reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) practices/outputs that are relevant for their fields and by designing a training & certification program with their feedback, we have raised awareness on a more diverse set of practices/outputs, in line with RROR, and of their relevance. This promoted a widespread network of ambassadors in the institution that promoted this program with their students and colleagues.

Finally, through dissemination activities at the institution, in scientific meetings nationally and abroad, we had the opportunity to build a multi- and interdisciplinary collaborative network to discuss research assessment.

Given that the current pilot happened within a particular institution, the University of Coimbra, we welcome future single or cross-institutional collaborations to pilot this type of program in other organizations, to better understand generalizable lessons and guidance but also local specificities. This would advance research and knowledge on implementation-focused programs targeted to improve research practice and deliver appropriate recognition & reward.

In the next section we translate this learning process into a Guide.

Implementation Guide 2

2.1. Vision and mission

In the last few years, initiatives, coalitions and recommendations (e.in, San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment¹⁸; UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science¹⁹; Metrics Tide²⁰; Hong Kong Principles²¹; Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment;), tools and use cases (Reformscape, DORA²²; UKRI Primers Across Disciplines²³; graspOS course on Rethinking Research Assessment²⁴), agreements (CoARA²⁵ ARRA²⁶), mechanisms (CoARA Boost²⁷), frameworks and instruments (iNORMS SCOPE²⁸; DORA Practical Guide²⁹; UK OR4

¹⁸ Reference: DORA, <https://sfdora.org/>

¹⁹ Reference: <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about>

²⁰ Reference: UKRI: The Metrics Tide: <https://www.ukri.org/publications/review-of-metrics-in-research-assessment-and-management/>

²¹ Reference: Resources on the Hong Kong principles: <https://www.wcrif.org/guidance/hong-kong-principles>

²² Reference: <https://sfdora.org/reformscape/>

²³ Reference: UKRN across disciplines listing use cases: <https://www.ukrn.org/disciplines/>

²⁴ Reference: OpenPlato graspOS course, <https://graspos.eu/?view=article&id=195&catid=8>

²⁵ Reference: Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment – CoARA, <https://www.coara.org/>

²⁶ Reference: CoARA: Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment: <https://www.coara.org/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>

²⁷ Reference: Strengthening CoARA and Enabling Systemic Reform of Research Assessment - A Booster, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101131826> ; <https://www.coara.org/coara-boost-cascade-funding/coara-boost-project/>

²⁸ Reference: iNORMS SCOPE: <https://inorms.net/scope-framework-for-research-evaluation/> ; Himanen L, Conte E, Gauffriau M *et al.* *F1000Research* 2024, 12:1241, <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.140810.2>

²⁹ Reference: Allen, L., Barbour, V., Cobey, K., Faulkes, Z., Hazlett, H., Lawrence, R., Lima, G., Massah, F., & Schmidt, R. (2025). A Practical Guide to Implementing Responsible Research Assessment at Research Performing Organizations. Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15000683>

Implementation guide³⁰) were created on why reforming the way we assess research and researchers is important, what we should value, and how to facilitate the change, the challenge happens at the particular context and where to start the change within an organization. This is our contribution.

This Guide aligns, in principle and in practice, with the vision of CoARA and of other research assessment reform movements. During the past year, this institutional pilot project - TREASURE - allowed us to build a program to set the groundwork for testing changes in reform of research assessment at the University of Coimbra, a research performing organization (RPO) in Southern Europe, Portugal. During this period, we were able to learn from successes and hurdles. We now translate this learning process into the development of this Guide.

Empowering the future generation of researchers, while formally recognizing & rewarding them for good practices and outputs in line with reproducible, reusable, and open research is essential to drive change in research & scholar culture, improving research quality, and positioning institutions as leaders in responsible and reliable research.

Following the wise words of others before us (DORA Practical Guide, CoARA ARRA, iNORMS SCOPE framework), there is no single recipe that will fit all organizations or entities. However, there are also

Basic supervisory principles for this Guide:

- Consider nature and **diversity** of science, research and scholarship (CoARA commitment 1)
- Foster **co-creation** environments in which all members can participate in the change process (CoARA commitment 2)
- Promote organizations exchange and use of information **for mutual learning** (CoARA commitment 8)
- Respect **autonomy** of research organizations in defining the evaluation of their researchers (CoARA ARRA Principles for overarching conditions) aligned with their **values** (iNORMS SCOPE framework step – Start with what you value) and strategic **goals**
- **Evidence** should inform revision and improvement of research assessment frameworks and reforms (CoARA commitment 10)

³⁰ UK Reproducibility Network. 2024. Recognising and rewarding open research. <https://recognition.ukrn-openresearch.ac.uk/>

common factors that facilitate change and activities we can transfer or adapt to other research institutions.

This Guide is therefore meant to be used by anyone or any organization that wants to implement a similar program to motivate researchers in their early career stages to adopt reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs at different levels - within their research group, research center or department, course, institutes or faculties.

Learning shared through this Guide will evolve through time, as the program runs and new knowledge is gathered. New updates will either result in a new version of this Guide or published elsewhere.

This Guide would not have been possible without the contributions of all participants in the pilot phase and the current training and certification program. We sincerely thank the course coordinators, researchers, supervisors, and university leadership who supported and enabled the program. We are also deeply grateful to the core team members, librarians, science managers, and external board members for their contributions and shared insight and expertise. Last but certainly not least—indeed, as the primary target group and the next generation of researchers—we genuinely thank all Master’s and PhD candidates involved: those who represented their peers on the Local Advisory Board, those who shared their insights beyond the Board, and those currently participating in the first edition of the TREASURE program. To all, our sincere appreciation.

2.2. Steps towards implementation

In this section we present and further develop the key steps to implementing a program to reward early or first stage researchers for implementing reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs. We used lessons learned from the TREASURE program, related external resources (e.g., DORA Practical Guide for RPOs) and other resources that although not directly related, provide insight on key steps to (e.g., INOSC StarterKit,

<https://www.startyourosc.com/> - building of communities, attracting and engaging members, and planning for long-term sustainability).

- **Plan how to implement the change:** as with any other project, you need to start by clarifying who is the target population and the key stakeholders, and what are the outputs of the pilot implementation exercise - what should be created with the stakeholders, what should be offered at the institution level, and when and how the different participants will contribute. This includes also detailing the different phases of the pilot exercise, allowing that outputs from each phase of the program can inform later phases;
- **Engage the community and ensure its alignment, during development and after program launch:** For the defined target population and key stakeholders, strategies to engage them and to give visibility to the project/program should be identified. We highlight two different moments to engage the community: (1) program development, engaging the target public and key actors to whom co-create the program; (2) program launch, to attract the participants that will take the program;
- **Co-create the change to implement:** You will need to identify an appropriate program structure (what mechanisms to develop to provide training, promote change, and deliver recognition & reward; what type of rewards and for whom), and who should be involved in developing solutions. Designed choices should be aligned with the objectives of the assessment framework—starting small and implementing well;
- **Find synergies:** Planned changes should be integrated strategically by identifying where the reform plan aligns with the institution’s broader strategic goals. This ensures that efforts are mutually reinforced and can be applied through identified institutional synergies;
- **Monitor the program:** To ensure meaningful impact, it is important to monitor progress through measurable and relevant indicators;
- **Assess the institutional maturity level and available resources:** It is important to assess the organization’s level of maturity. After the first stage and development of

relevant stakeholders, program structure and criteria, the institutional maturity can be assessed by (a) conducting baseline assessments to test the assessment criteria and key performance indicators, or (b) mapping existing resources and institutional capacity, including human resources, training programs, and available toolkits.

- **Plan for growth and long-term sustainability:** Finally, programs should be designed with long-term sustainability in mind. This includes planning for both short- and long-term continuity and embedding continuous improvement processes through the use of quality management principles and tools.

These steps are further developed in the following subsections.

2.2.1. Plan how to implement the change

- **Define your target population and key actors**

If you plan to target **Early-stage researchers (ESRs)**, you should decide if you plan to start in one or more **disciplinary fields**, or if you want to do this at the **institution** (multi-disciplinary) level. Working at the institutional level brings **challenges** – how to reach and involve the different faculties or centers, and how to align the different disciplines under the same framework while respecting epistemic diversity.

You also need to define what are your target **cycle of studies**: undergraduate (1st cycle – bachelor or licentiate) and/or graduate (2nd – master’s, and 3rd cycles - PhD). Working with different cycles of studies may bring challenges related to, for instance, the level of knowledge and experience that the students have with research methods and practice (1st cycle students may not have research experiences yet) and the time that student’s have to complete their research and degree. At the same time, starting earlier may promote relevant training in early career stages, where these can be more easily built, and aligned incentives.

Irrespective of the range of the program, be sure that beside your target population you involve also the **key actors** (e.g. course coordinators, supervisors, directors of R&D centers where

students develop their research plans) that work closely with your target population and hold relevant positions to drive structured change.

For strategies to bring these members to the discussion, see section (2.2.3) on Community engagement (Part I).

- **Project outputs**

Think about how you can introduce change – what you want to **promote** (e.g., knowledge, skills; principles, practices) and how you can provide the proper **incentives** and **recognition & reward** mechanisms to motivate the targeted population to adopt what is being promoted.

You will also need to think about what you want to **create** with the target public and key actors (e.g., list of practices/outputs to support; qualitative assessment and criteria) and at what **level** can this be applied (e.g., specific optional training programs; faculty courses; degree level or additional to the degree) to support what you want to promote.

Finally, mechanisms to promote commitment from all involved should be created (e.g., agreements between supervisors and students; implementation plan templates).

Knowing this will facilitate the identification and definition of a feasible **structure** for what you want

PLANNING - Key points

- Identify **key steps** in the change you want to implement

Start by **clarifying**:

- who is the **target population** and the key stakeholders,
 - include range of application (disciplinary or institutional),
- what are the **outputs** of the pilot implementation exercise,
 - what should be created with the stakeholders,
 - what should be offered (institution, faculties or R&D centers level),
- when and how the different participants will **contribute**,
- the project **timeline**, detailing the different phase of the pilot exercise.

Identify **risks & mitigations**:

- Think what can be the **challenges** of involving different disciplines and different cycles of studies, and potential **solutions**

to create (e.g. informal or formal program; create new or embedded in existing courses; disciplinary or cross-course).

- **Project timeline**

There may be advantages in defining different **stages** for the project, depending on what you plan to build at your institution.

To introduce changes in current institutional, faculty or disciplinary assessment frameworks, you may need to understand better what is already in place and what is currently valued at your institution. During stage 1, you may do this **review process**, to better decide what you want to target for change. You can do this assessment with the community during the co-creation process, to better inform what you want to develop with them, identifying drivers and barriers, and where the community finds most value.

In stage 2 may further **develop and deliver the outputs** (e.g. programs to recognize & reward skills).

During stage 3, you put the delivered outputs into practice (**launch**) and start **monitoring** their impact.

2.2.2. Engage the community and ensure its alignment, during development and after program launch

For the defined target population and key stakeholders, strategies to engage them and to give visibility to the project/program should be identified. To attract the target audience, key actors, and future participants in the program being built, it is important to give visibility to the program. This can be made through the creation of an institutional website, or by creating news and communication pieces that can disseminate the program through the institution, faculties and other relevant institutional webpages.

Community engagement may happen in two different time periods: (1) during program development, to attract representatives of the target public and stakeholders, (2) during program launch, to attract participants to take the program.

- **Engage the community in the change process**

The target population will define the program audience and key actors to involve in the implementation of the program, and strategies to engage and communicate with them. It is important that these strategies are tailored to the specific audience.

To start the discussion, the constitution of **Working Groups** (WG) or of **Local Advisory Boards** (LABs) may be useful, as long as they are constituted by the relevant members.

When planning who to invite for a LAB, think who may bring **added value** – roles, disciplines, courses. Also, try to find balance in the number to include, aware that you may not be able that all the members be present in all the meetings – try to avoid redundancy of roles but plan to have more than one member that can provide the relevant feedback for her/his specific role, research field or course.

The **constitution** of these groups or boards may take longer than expected (e.g. lack of response to invites; unavailability and need to replace invited members), so it is important to plan and allow enough time to receive more than one set of responses. Also, you can try snowball strategies – invite course coordinators first and ask them what other members from their field of research (e.g., supervisors from their research groups) and/or course (e.g., students from the course they coordinate) could be of value to the board.

Be sure to **recognize** their role and participation at the end (e.g., website, outputs from the program with proper contributor roles).

- **Attract participants to the launched program**

After its development, you will need to attract participants for the launched program. For this you need to **disseminate** the program widely and convey a motivating and simple message about the added value of the program. In large institutions this may pose bigger **challenges** – for instance, due to absence or unreliability of channels that can widely disseminate program information, or due to different research cultures across faculties.

When planning how to disseminate, do not forget to provide an **institutional** brand for the program. For instance, an institutional website and logo increases **visibility** and will allow people to find and know more about the program, and give more **credibility** to what was created and is being offered.

To convey the message:

- clearly identify what you are doing (e.g., develop skills in open research; recognize diverse research contributions and outputs; change research assessment), why you are doing it, and value offered for all;
- clearly identify who is involved: if the leadership is involved, make sure to include this information as this may provide additional motive; also members of the community may more easily participate in programs where they feel their field was/is represented (e.g.,

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

- Key points

- **Engage the community** in the change process
 - Create **local** working groups or advisory boards
 - Ensure **representation** of the target public and key actors
 - Properly **recognize** contributions made
- **Attract participants** to the launched program
 - Give **visibility** to the program
 - Give an **institutional seal** to the program
 - Disseminate the program created
 - Adapt the messages considering the target public, showing the added value of the program

Identify **risks & mitigations**:

- Think what can be the **challenges** of involving different disciplines and different cycles of studies, and potential **solutions**

visibility of past participants, or members of the LAB that are students in their field may act like a driver);

- identify the communication channels that can reach the community of interest, and define the message (strategy) considering the target groups (e.g., for course coordinators, supervisors, students - show what is the added value from participating);
- identify who can act as hubs to disseminate messages through their own networks (e.g. course coordinators can disseminate the program to the students; supervisors can engage the students they supervise, but also other students in their R&D unit or research group; the leadership can involve directors of faculties).

2.2.3. Co-create the change to implement

To be able to enroll your target population and bring change through them, you will need to identify an appropriate **program structure** (e.g., what mechanisms should be created, adapted to provide training, promote change, and deliver recognition & reward), and **who should be involved** in developing solutions. Designed solutions should be aligned with the objectives of the assessment framework.

- **Co-create the program**

To facilitate the co-creation exercise, use **available frameworks** to help you design your sessions. SCOPE (Himanen et al., 2024; iNORMS) is a framework specifically designed to walk the path with the institutions on the research assessment reform, respecting their pace, values and strategic needs. This will help you design how to identify values, and create frameworks, but also the importance of probing the created framework against unintended consequences and discrimination of members that it may bring, allowing definition of mitigation strategies.

To start the conversation with the members with whom you will co-create the program, be aware of **differences in the expertise level** in the particular topics you are bringing to the discussion – e.g., new research assessment frameworks and open research or reproducibility concepts – these may act as a barrier. To address this, you may start by giving relevant information about the research assessment reform, the open research movement, and the value added by these initiatives to promote more rigorous, credible and robust knowledge. Moreover, the constitution of an **external board of experts** may be useful – to provide relevant feedback and complement what has been built locally, but also to provide solutions for identified challenges and shared solutions that worked in their home institutions.

Also, it may be more efficient to **offer a starting suggestion for LAB members to critique, rather** than asking the members to design something from scratch. To prepare the sessions, bring some material so that members can provide feedback, curate, review, and add relevant practices and outputs from their own fields (e.g., design a list of practices/outputs to be recognized and value, asking for their feedback and to add things that are relevant for their specific fields and that they would like to see recognized and rewarded; suggest different formats for the program to deliver and ask for pros and cons; list some indicators for criteria and ask them to review them).

PROGRAM CO-CREATION

- Key points

- How to **design** the co-creation sessions, and what **available tools** can you use
- To receive valuable **feedback**, what **information** should you bring to the table
- Discuss the change **added value**
- Identify **recognition & reward mechanisms** that work in the institution
- How to **reward all** involved in the change process
- Start **small** and design for success

Identify **risks & mitigations**:

- How you can **level knowledge** to start the conversation
- Anticipate **epistemic diversity** and how to respect and represent different ways of knowing (nature of research)
- Anticipate **resistance** to change

Depending on the defined **range** for your program (one or two similar epistemic or disciplinary fields, or an institutional multi-disciplinary program), be sure to consider both the **advantages** and the **challenges** that **epistemic diversity** may bring (e.g., different epistemologies and knowledge system modes, different terminologies) and try to specifically address this in the co-creation events or meetings. You may present them with some practices and types of outputs, and briefly explain them to clarify what is about, and then ask if these are relevant and/or apply or not to their field (feasibility), how they are implemented in the specific fields, and what is the field denomination, if any.

In the end, be sure to **probe** and to bring awareness on downsides of the program, who can discriminate, and how this can be mitigated.

- **Show the added value**

Given the planned introduction of change, **resistance** may be found among some of the members (i) who are not so familiar with the new concepts, (ii) who see conflict with their usual practice, (iii) additional efforts for which they will have neither the skills nor the time, or (iv) . To address these challenges, it may be useful to design exercises (e.g., brainstorming) to identify advantages and opportunities that the suggested change and planned program may bring for each member (e.g., skills acquired; more diverse outputs beyond publication; reputation added). It may also be useful to acknowledge fears (e.g. of data sharing) and to counter-act based on evidence (e.g., personal and sensitive data may be deposited in trusted repositories under restricted access protocols, while being FAIR and with associated open metadata) and the added value (e.g., sharing data reduces research waste, provides more outputs from the same project, increases visibility of the researcher).

- **Identify recognition & reward mechanisms that work in the institution**

Although there are a lot of training resources available on reproducible, reusable and open research, one of the key challenges is to translate the training received to the research that is actually done, and how to recognize the students and researchers for implementation with quality.

To identify potential solutions, involving the **institutional leadership** may be relevant, in particular **experts** in the crediting system – what type of incentives can be used? What type of recognition and/or prizes are possible to offer at the institution/faculty/center? And for that, which type of programs (e.g. formal, informal) are best suited? Examples of possible rewards are prizes and awards, travel to scientific meetings or course participation awards. For recognition, this can be done more or less formal through recognition of champions, ambassadors in the program page, and certification in the curricula.

Some concerns may be raised regarding the rewards that can be offered and, crucially, to whom – when motivating for change, it is important to **include and recognize all in the process**, and not only the target population (e.g., rewarding students but not their supervisors).

- **When implemented, start small and design for success**

To ensure program success, start small: a few reproducible, reusable and open research practices and/or outputs, planned towards quality can do much better than trying everything at once. Programs that introduce small, feasible steps for change may be more successful than those that try everything at start.

A few strategies can be found at Heise et al. (2023), such as:

- Ask the students to create shortlists of practices and/or outputs that are relevant and feasible to implement in their research projects or workplans and are feasible for the

cycle of studies targeted (time available). This will facilitate starting the discussion with supervisors and other relevant members, to decide what to actually implement;

- Ask for implementation plans to guide students on the “who,” “what,” “when,” and “how” for each selected practice. Include risk and mitigation plans for identified issues.

2.2.4. Find synergies

Planned changes should be integrated strategically by identifying where the reform plan aligns with the institution’s broader strategic goals. This ensures that efforts are mutually reinforced and can be applied through identified institutional synergies.

By involving the leadership of the institution, or by connecting with formal or informal networks, you may identify additional initiatives, projects ongoing and institutional strategic goals to which the project may contribute, finding synergies in the ongoing tasks. Also, you may build synergy with ongoing projects and initiatives, involving others that may have built expertise.

For this, map the relevant stakeholders for the tasks defined – this may mean persons, projects or initiatives in place. It is important not to reinvent the wheel or start from scratch; find who may know – this is particularly relevant for big institutions – having the leadership involved may help identify relevant information that would be hard to identify in another way.

FIND SYNERGIES

- Key points

- Know what the institutional **strategic lines** and **goals** are
- Plan how to **integrate** the envisioned change within those strategic goals
- Involve the **leadership**, propose solutions and work with them towards synergetic goals
- Map other **relevant stakeholders** with whom you can work synergistically

2.2.5. Monitor change through program measurable indicators

To ensure meaningful impact, it is important to monitor progress through **measurable** and **relevant indicators**, in a feasible manner. Indicators may relate to program enrollment but also to their impact in the specific environment (e.g., research groups, R&D centers, faculty, institution). Think about how you can properly assess program **impact** by considering other institutional initiatives (e.g., can these impact be measured independently?). For this, information in sections 2.2.6 and 2.2.7 may be useful – assess baseline to measure impact, how to plan for sustainability of the program and its monitoring, and if meta-research capacity and tools can be useful to measure change and success.

Be sure you **allocate** enough **resources** (human resources, time) to be able to measure program impact at defined temporal points.

2.2.6. Assess institutional maturity level and available resources

It is important to assess the organization’s level of maturity to benchmark the program. After the first stage and development of relevant stakeholders, program structure and criteria, the institutional maturity can be checked by assessing the state-of-the-art in terms of the change to implement (e.g., assessing thesis, dissertations or research works published prior to the program delivery using the developed criteria) and by mapping of existing resources and institutional capacity, including human resources, training programs, and available toolkits.

- **Assess the institutional current maturity level**

State of the art assessments facilitate definition of what to track and monitor, testing the feasibility of future monitoring exercises, their improvement and measurement the program impact. Some institutions in the UK have used self-assessment tools to perform this evaluation (e.g., maturity framework and tool developed by the UK Reproducibility Network, 2024:

<https://recognition.ukrn-openresearch.ac.uk/maturity-framework.html>). Depending on the intended change and target public, more tuned assessment exercises may be considered. The assessment exercise should consider the criteria developed and that will be implemented and tested.

- **Identify existing resources at your organization**

Be sure to track the available resources in your institution: this will help identify human resources that bring **expertise** (e.g., researchers, professors, technicians, science managers, librarians, etc.) but also ongoing **projects** and available **training**, minimizing creating from scratch and fostering collaboration.

Both exercises document the "maturity level" of the institution in terms of the change you want to implement, providing you with a relevant network, resources and materials that you may invite and use in the program (e.g., teaching staff; training materials) or reuse and adapt in later project/program stages (e.g., protocols for monitoring change; search strategies, sampling frames, abstraction protocols).

TREASURE supporting outputs:

Identify institutional resources:

- **Milestone M3.0** - Trainings assessment and gap analysis. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17078623>
- **Deliverable D3.0** - Training program: List of trainings and resources to support implementation of reproducible, reusable and open research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093856>

2.2.7. Plan for growth and long-term sustainability

Finally, programs should be designed and delivered with long-term sustainability in mind (Mayne, 2020). This includes planning for both short- and long-term continuity and embedding

continuous improvement processes using quality management principles and tools (for an overview of key concepts, see Dirnagl et al., 2018). Also, the program should be embedded in a sustainable structure that does not depend on precarious and temporary human resources.

We address some **key points** to consider:

- What will be the **structure** and who will be responsible for its maintenance (e.g., institutional leaders, services, teaching staff) – what are the type of employment contracts and conditions or the members involved? Are there plans to embed this in long-term structures?
- What are the relevant **resources** that allow their sustainability – are there allocated financial resources or grants applications should be considered?
- Who (**human resources**) will do the monitoring and check the quality and impact of the program for constant improvement?
- How to **scale** the program (Mayne & Johnson, 2015) – if you started by specific domains, how to scale to other fields, departments and faculties? And how to collaborate with other institutions to translate the program cross-institutionally?
- Plan to use **meta-research** tools to improve and scale what has been created – is there built capacity in the institution? Can this be built? How? What are the relevant fields of meta-research that are most useful here (Roberts et al., 2022)?

2.3. Concluding remarks

The development and implementation of the TREASURE program in a RPO covering a high range of disciplines and research fields allowed us to build a vision of drivers and barriers that can facilitate and difficult the creation of an innovative program that aims to promote change in how research and researchers are currently assessed.

It is nevertheless important to consider that at each particular institution the path will necessarily be unique given the institutional *values*, *strategic goals*, and the existing *structures and mechanisms* - being aware of what these are is a key step to define where change can start and how to implement it.

Through these institutional trails different solutions will be found, and this will also be crucial to understand where our paths cross, were we can guide and learn from each other, and were the steps need to be locally grounded.

We sincerely hope that this exercise and Guide can be useful for others in their path for change – such as CoARA, DORA and so many other inspiring research assessment reform initiatives have guided ours.

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